

An Observation on Hollow Viscus Perforation: Re-Appraisal of Its Magnitude and Treatment Modalities

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Abstract:

Background: Hollow viscus perforation (HVP) is a serious surgical emergency that presents with high morbidity and mortality. The non-traumatic causes of HVP, including peptic ulcer disease, appendicitis, and diverticulitis, are often associated with lifestyle factors such as smoking, alcohol consumption, and NSAID use. Timely diagnosis and appropriate management are critical in improving patient outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to assess the prevalence, risk factors, management, and outcomes of non-traumatic hollow viscus perforation in patients at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted from November 2019 to October 2020, including 126 patients diagnosed with non-traumatic hollow viscus perforation. Data were collected on patient demographics, clinical presentation, diagnostic methods, surgical interventions, complications, and outcomes. Statistical analysis was performed to determine the associations between risk factors and surgical outcomes.

Results: The study found that the majority of patients were male (84.13%), with the highest incidence in the 30-39 age group (28.57%). The most common risk factors were smoking (47.62%) and NSAID use (31.74%). Duodenal perforations were the most common (60.31%), and Modified Graham's Patch repair was the most frequently performed surgery (69.84%). Postoperative complications included wound infection (49.21%) and respiratory issues (26.98%). The overall mortality rate was 4.76%, with most patients discharged within 14 days (80.95%).

Conclusion: Non-traumatic hollow viscus perforation remains a significant surgical emergency, predominantly affecting middle-aged males. Peptic ulcer disease continues to be the leading cause, with smoking and NSAID use as major risk factors. Surgical management is generally effective, though complications are common. Early diagnosis and timely intervention are crucial to improving outcomes.

Recommendations: Public health campaigns targeting smoking cessation and the responsible use of NSAIDs should be promoted. Furthermore, improving access to timely medical care and advanced diagnostic tools in rural and underserved areas can reduce mortality rates associated with hollow viscus perforation.

Keywords: Hollow viscus perforation, peptic ulcer disease, surgical intervention, postoperative complications, risk factors.

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Introduction

(HVP) is a life-threatening emergency often associated with high morbidity and mortality. It involves the rupture of the gastrointestinal tract, leading to the leakage of intestinal contents into the peritoneal cavity, causing peritonitis and sepsis. The most common sites of perforation are the duodenum, ileum, appendix, and stomach, with peptic ulcer disease being a significant cause of duodenal perforations [1]. Non-traumatic causes of HVP are frequently linked to underlying conditions such as peptic ulcers, diverticulitis, appendicitis, and malignancies, along with an increasing prevalence of lifestyle factors such as smoking, alcohol use, and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID)

consumption [2,3]. These perforations often present as acute abdominal emergencies and require prompt surgical intervention to minimize complications.

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD), although reduced due to advances in medical therapy, remains a leading cause of duodenal perforation. Helicobacter pylori infection and chronic NSAID use are well-established risk factors for PUD and, consequently, hollow viscus perforation [4]. Smoking and alcohol consumption further exacerbate these risks, making lifestyle modifications critical in prevention [5]. The pathophysiology of perforation involves increased acid secretion and mucosal damage, leading to ulcer formation and eventual rupture in some patients [6].

Perforations are typically diagnosed via imaging studies, including abdominal X-rays and computed tomography (CT) scans, which can identify free gas or fluid in the peritoneal cavity [7].

Surgical intervention remains the primary treatment modality, and the choice of procedure is determined by the perforation site and the patient's overall condition. Techniques such as Graham's patch repair, appendectomy, and resection with anastomosis are common, depending on the location and severity of the perforation [8]. Early diagnosis and prompt surgical management have been shown to significantly reduce morbidity and mortality rates. However, despite these interventions, postoperative complications like wound infections, sepsis, and respiratory issues are prevalent, and managing these complications remains a challenge [9].

The global burden of HVP remains substantial, especially in low- and middle-income countries, where delays in presentation and limited access to healthcare contribute to worse outcomes. Addressing these issues through public health initiatives and improved healthcare access could play a significant role in reducing the incidence of HVP and its associated complications [10]. This study aims to assess the prevalence, risk factors, management, and outcomes of non-traumatic hollow viscus perforation in patients at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a hospital-based prospective observational analysis conducted over 12 months, from November 2019 to October 2020.

Study Location and Participants: The study was carried out in the Department of General Surgery at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna. A total of 126 patients admitted to the surgical emergency department with a clinical and radiological diagnosis of hollow viscus perforation were included in the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Patients diagnosed with non-traumatic hollow viscus perforation were included if they underwent emergency surgical intervention during the study period. Patients with traumatic injuries (blunt or penetrating), genitourinary perforations (e.g., ruptured ectopic pregnancy or bladder rupture), malignancy-associated perforations, or those treated outside the institution were excluded.

Data Collection and Preoperative Management: A detailed clinical history was obtained for all patients, focusing on risk factors such as smoking, alcohol consumption, NSAID use, and socioeconomic status. Clinical examination emphasized abdominal signs like tenderness, guarding, rigidity, and systemic symptoms such as fever or hypotension. Diagnostic investigations

included complete blood counts, renal function tests, electrolytes, and specific tests like Widal test or blood cultures in suspected cases of sepsis or enteric fever. Imaging studies, including an abdominal X-ray in the erect position and ultrasonography, were performed to identify free air or fluid in the peritoneal cavity. Preoperatively, patients were resuscitated with intravenous fluids, nasogastric decompression, and broad-spectrum antibiotics (ampicillin, gentamicin, and metronidazole). Vital signs and urine output were closely monitored to ensure hemodynamic stability.

Surgical Intervention: Exploratory laparotomy was performed under epidural, spinal, or general anesthesia. The type of surgical intervention was determined based on the site and severity of the perforation. Peptic ulcer perforations were managed primarily by Modified Graham's Patch repair, while appendicular perforations required appendectomy. Small bowel perforations were treated with primary repair for localized defects or resection and anastomosis with ileostomy in cases of severe contamination. Gastric perforations were repaired using primary closure or an omental patch, and jejunal perforations underwent primary repair. The abdominal cavity was thoroughly irrigated with saline, and appropriate drains were placed to minimize postoperative complications.

Postoperative Management: Postoperative care included continued nasogastric decompression, intravenous fluids, and antibiotic therapy tailored to culture and sensitivity results. Patients were monitored closely for complications, such as wound infections, respiratory issues, dyselectrolytemia, or sepsis. Recovery was assessed daily, and patients were discharged upon clinical stabilization. Follow-up evaluations were conducted for a period of 3 to 12 months to monitor long-term outcomes.

Outcome Measures: The study focused on both primary and secondary outcomes. The primary outcomes included morbidity due to complications like wound infections, dyselectrolytemia, and sepsis, as well as mortality rates. Secondary outcomes examined the duration of hospital stays, effectiveness of different surgical procedures, and the relationship between demographic factors, clinical features, and treatment outcomes.

Data Analysis: Data from all patients were systematically recorded and analyzed to identify trends in patient demographics, risk factors, clinical presentations, and treatment outcomes. The findings were compared with existing literature, and results were summarized in tables and charts for clarity and insight.

Results

This study included 126 patients diagnosed with non-traumatic hollow viscus perforation who

underwent surgical intervention. The age of participants ranged from 12 to 74 years, with a mean age of 36.8 years. The highest incidence was observed in the 30–39 age group (28.57%), followed

by the 40–49 age group (22.22%). Males constituted 84.13% (n=106), and females accounted for 15.87% (n=20), with a male-to-female ratio of 5.3:1.

Table 1: Age-Wise Distribution of Patients

Age Group (years)	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
10–19	18	14.29
20–29	20	15.87
30–39	36	28.57
40–49	28	22.22
50–59	14	11.11
≥60	10	7.94
Total	126	100

Among the participants, the majority (35%) belonged to the lower-middle class, while 27% were from the upper-middle class.

Table 2: Socioeconomic Status of Patients

Socioeconomic Class	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Upper Class	0	0
Upper Middle Class	34	27.0
Lower Middle Class	44	35.0
Upper Lower Class	30	23.81
Lower Class	18	14.29
Total	126	100

The most common risk factors were smoking (47.62%) and NSAID use (31.74%). Alcohol consumption was noted in 20.63% of cases.

Table 3: Risk Factors Among Patients

Risk Factor	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Smoking	60	47.62
Alcohol	26	20.63
Smoking + Alcohol	32	25.39
NSAID Use	40	31.74

Abdominal pain was the universal symptom (100%), followed by abdominal distension

(76.19%), constipation or diarrhea (58.73%), and vomiting (53.97%).

Table 4: Clinical Presentation of Patients

Symptom	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Pain Abdomen	126	100.0
Abdominal Distension	96	76.19
Constipation/Diarrhea	74	58.73
Vomiting	68	53.97
Fever	54	42.86
Shock	6	4.76

Radiological findings revealed gas under the diaphragm in 82.54% of cases, and ultrasonography detected free peritoneal fluid in 80.95% of cases.

Laboratory tests showed raised total leukocyte counts in 71.42% and raised serum creatinine in 28.57%.

Table 5: Diagnostic Findings

Diagnostic Modality	Finding	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
X-Ray Abdomen	Gas under diaphragm	104	82.54
Ultrasonography	Free fluid	102	80.95
Laboratory: Raised TLC	(>11,000 cells/cmm)	90	71.42
Laboratory: Raised Creatinine	(>1.5 mg/dL)	36	28.57
Hypokalemia	(<3.5 mmol/L)	18	14.28
Hyponatremia	(<135 mmol/L)	28	22.22

The most common site was the duodenum (60.31%), followed by the appendix (17.46%) and ileum (11.11%).

Table 6: Distribution by Site of Perforation

Site of Perforation	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Duodenum	76	60.31
Appendix	22	17.46
Ileum	14	11.11
Gastric Antrum	12	9.52
Jejunum	2	1.59

Modified Graham’s Patch repair was the most frequently performed procedure (69.84%), followed by appendectomy (17.46%).

Table 7: Surgical Procedures Performed

Surgical Procedure	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Modified Graham’s Patch Repair	88	69.84
Appendectomy	22	17.46
Resection and Anastomosis	2	1.59
Primary Repair with Ileostomy	10	7.94
Jejunal Repair	2	1.59

Wound infection was the most common complication (49.21%), followed by dyselectrolytemia (34.92%) and respiratory infections (26.98%).

Table 8: Postoperative Complications

Complication	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Wound Infection	62	49.21
Respiratory Infection	34	26.98
Dyselectrolytemia	44	34.92
Sepsis	22	17.46

The duration of hospital stay ranged from 8 to 26 days, with most patients (80.95%) discharged with in 14 days. The morbidity rate was 53.97%, and the mortality rate was 4.76%.

Table 9: Hospital Stay Duration

Hospital Stay (days)	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
8–14	102	80.95
15–21	18	14.29
>21	6	4.76

Table 10: Surgical Outcomes

Outcome	Number of Patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Recovered	52	41.27
Recovered with Complications	68	53.97
Mortality	6	4.76

Discussion

The majority of the patients were male (84.13%), with a male-to-female ratio of 5.3:1, and the most affected age group was 30–39 years (28.57%). This age distribution suggests that hollow viscus perforation predominantly affects middle-aged adults, likely due to higher exposure to lifestyle-related risk factors, including smoking and NSAID use. Socioeconomic analysis showed that most patients belonged to lower-middle (35%) and upper-middle (27%) socioeconomic classes, indicating that socioeconomic factors, potentially including limited access to healthcare or delayed presentation, may influence the incidence and outcomes of this condition.

Smoking was the most common risk factor, affecting 47.62% of patients, followed by NSAID use (31.74%) and alcohol consumption (20.63%). These findings align with existing literature, emphasizing modifiable lifestyle factors as critical contributors to the condition. The predominant clinical presentations included abdominal pain (100%), abdominal distension (76.19%), and constipation or diarrhea (58.73%), reflecting the classical signs of hollow viscus perforation. This consistent symptomatology underscores the importance of early clinical recognition to facilitate timely diagnosis and management.

Diagnostic findings were primarily supported by imaging and laboratory investigations. Radiological evidence of gas under the diaphragm was observed in 82.54% of cases, while ultrasonography detected free fluid in 80.95%. Laboratory results showed elevated total leukocyte counts in 71.42% of patients, indicating systemic inflammation or sepsis.

These findings highlight the essential role of prompt diagnostic imaging and laboratory tests in confirming the clinical suspicion of perforation.

Duodenal perforations were the most common (60.31%), followed by appendicular (17.46%) and ileal perforations (11.11%). Peptic ulcer disease was identified as the primary etiology, consistent with global trends in developing regions. Surgical intervention was tailored to the perforation site and included Modified Graham’s Patch repair in 69.84% of patients and appendectomy in 17.46%. These findings suggest that standard surgical approaches remain effective for managing the majority of hollow viscus perforations.

Postoperative complications were common, with wound infections (49.21%) being the most frequent, followed by dyselectrolytemia (34.92%) and

respiratory infections (26.98%). Despite these complications, the mortality rate was relatively low at 4.76%, underscoring the effectiveness of surgical intervention and postoperative care. The average hospital stay was between 8 and 14 days for most patients, which reflects the typical recovery time for such cases.

Laparoscopic repair has emerged as an effective alternative to open repair for hollow viscus perforations, offering reduced surgical times and faster recovery. A randomized controlled trial demonstrated that laparoscopic repair significantly reduced the duration of surgery (105 minutes vs. 141 minutes) and allowed patients to resume normal activities earlier (4.5 days vs. 11.8 days) [11]. A prospective study on prognostic factors found that delayed presentation, advanced age, and specific perforation types, such as colonic and ileal, were

associated with increased morbidity and mortality. Duodenal perforations were the most common, followed by appendicular perforations, with postoperative chest infections being the most frequent complication [12]. Another observational study highlighted peptic ulcer perforations as the most common etiology, particularly among patients aged 40-60 years. Smoking and alcohol use were notable risk factors. Ileal perforations were more common in younger populations with typhoid fever. The study reported an overall mortality rate of 4% [13]. A study during the COVID-19 pandemic investigated triple drain placement for managing perforated hollow viscus in rural areas. This method reduced the need for tertiary care transfers, addressing the challenges posed by resource constraints. Outcomes included lower rates of intra-abdominal abscess and better postoperative recovery [14].

Conclusion

The study highlights the significant burden of hollow viscus perforation among middle-aged males in this region, with smoking, NSAID use, and socioeconomic status playing pivotal roles. Prompt diagnosis through clinical evaluation and imaging, followed by standard surgical management, yielded favourable outcomes in the majority of cases. However, the high morbidity rate emphasizes the need for improved postoperative care and strategies to address modifiable risk factors, potentially reducing the incidence and complications associated with this condition.

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